

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF 2-PHENOXYMETHYL-8-N-SUBSTITUTED AMINO CARBONYL METHYL-8-SUBSTITUTED-4(3H)-QUINAZOLONE (V)

Compound* No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	LD ₅₀	Anticonvulsant activity	
							Protection (%)	Mortality (%)
Ia	H	H	morpholinyl	110-112	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	1000	60	60
Ib	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	thiazolyl	139-140	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ SCl	1000	30	30
Ic	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	pyrrolidinyl	128-130	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	900	40	60
Id	H	H	pyrrolidinyl	120-121	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	980	50	50
Ie	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	cyclohexyl	145	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	1000	30	70
If	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	piperidinyl	105-107	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	850	20	80
Ig	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	thiazolyl	150-151	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	1000	60	40
Ih	H	H	thiazolyl	198-200	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	950	50	40
Ii	H	H	cyclohexyl	182	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄	1000	40	60
Ij	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	morpholinyl	201	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	1000	60	40
Ik	H	H	thiazolyl	215	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ SI	980	50	40
Il	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	piperidinyl	135	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄	1000	30	70
IIm	H	H	piperidinyl	170	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄	900	40	50
IIn	H	H	morpholinyl	140	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ I	850	50	40

* The compounds were obtained in about 60-64% yields.

Elemental analysis of C, H and N were obtained within $\pm 0.4\%$.

Ib.	NMR (CDCl ₃) δ ppm : 8.33 (s, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₈ -H), 7.63-6.85 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.83 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 8.25 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₂ -H), 7.60-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₃₋₄ -H), 7.80 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Ig.	8.30 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.61-6.84 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.83 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 8.13 (d, 1H, C ₂ -H), 7.4-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₃₋₄ -H), 7.80 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 2.5 (s, 3H, CH ₃), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Iii.	8.33 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.61-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.81 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 2.72 (m, 5H, Arom), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Iv.	7.75 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.32 (t, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₆ -H), 6.93 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₇ -H), 2.70 (m, 5H, Arom), 3.82 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).

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Synthesis of 1,2,4-Oxadiazolines Having Antifungal Activity

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Continuation of our work on the synthesis of new heterocyclic compounds^{1,2} having antifungal activity 1,2,4-oxadiazolines have been prepared by

the cycloaddition of benzonitrile oxide to 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines¹. The cycloaddition of benzonitrile oxide to 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines has been carried out at 0° using different solvents like ether, chloroform, etc. depending upon the solubility of the Schiff bases. Benzonitrile oxide was generated *in situ* by the reaction of bases like triethylamine or 14% sodium hydroxide on the hydroxamoyl chloride². A mixture of two products was obtained in each case. The major product has been found to be the cycloadduct (I) and the minor one is identified as dimer⁴ (II) of the nitrile oxide through its m.p. and m.m.p. The cycloadducts can have a structure either Ia or Ib.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	N% Found (Calcd.)
1.	H	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	7.75 (7.77)
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	81	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	7.52 (7.49)
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl	67	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	7.09 (7.10)
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	7.09 (7.10)
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	69	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Br	6.39 (6.38)

The infrared spectrum of the cycloadduct showed bands at 1680 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$). NMR spectrum in CDCl_3 of the cycloadduct (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) showed six methoxy protons at 6.1τ , 13 aromatic protons at 2.7τ and one proton on the C_5 of the oxadiazoline ring at 2.1τ . Such a low field shift of C_5 proton supported structure Ia rather than Ib in which proton is deshielded only by a nitrogen atom.

These 1,2,4-oxadiazolines (1 to 5) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis*, *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii* by employing standard method of spore germination inhibition. Three concentrations, viz., 1000, 500 and 250 ppm of each of the compounds, have been tried against all the test fungi. All the compounds possessed promising antifungal activity against the above fungi and caused 100% spore germination inhibition even at 250 ppm. The study at still lower concentration is in progress. These observations confirmed our earlier results that presence of methoxy phenyl ring in a compound helps in increasing its activity¹.

Experimental

1,2,4-Oxadiazoline (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$): 3,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde (2.41 g; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in ether (100 ml) and cooled in an ice bath to 0° . Benzhydroxamoyl chloride (1.1 g; 0.01 mole) in ether (20 ml) was then added with constant shaking and the contents were kept at 0° for some time. Triethylamine (1.2 ml) in ether (20 ml) was then added at a very slow rate with continuous shaking. When the addition was complete the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 0° for 2 hr. The ether layer was separated out and the residue was washed thrice with dry ether. The combined ether layer and the washings on evaporation of the solvent yielded crystalline solid which on recrystallization from benzene-petroleum ether mixture gave fine shining crystals, m.p. 65° (yield 85%).

Testing of the compounds against fungus: Three concentrations (250, 500 and 1000 ppm) of I ($\text{R}=\text{H}$) were taken and treated against fungus *Puccinia striiformis*. The treated spores were incubated for 18 hr and percent spore germination inhibition was calculated by counting 200 spores of each treatment. Spores incubated in water + respective solvent in which the compound is dissolved were used as control. The following

formula is used to calculate % spore germination inhibition.

$$\% \text{ Spore germination inhibition} = \frac{\text{Spore germination inhibition} - \text{Control}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Similarly, other 1,2,4-oxadiazolines were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis* and other fungi viz., *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii*.

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Chemical Examination of *Medicago sativa* Seeds

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MEDICAGO sativa¹⁻³ (Leguminosae), known as alfalfa or lucerne, is an erect, much branched annual herb. Its seeds are yellowish brown in colour, kidney shaped, rich in vitamin and enzyme. Looking to its nutritive value, it was thought interesting to investigate fixed oil and unsaponifiable matter from the seeds of this plant.

The crushed seeds of *Medicago sativa* were exhaustively extracted with pet. ether ($60-80^\circ$) and a yellowish brown coloured fixed oil (yield 8.50%) was obtained. The oil was found to have following physico-chemical values.

Specific gravity (25°)	...	0.9275
Refractive index	...	1.4624
Acid value	...	5.32
Saponification value	...	178.56
Iodine value	...	8.26
Acetyl value	...	99.50

100 g of the oil was saponified⁴ and the mixed acids (88 g) obtained. The mixed acids were resolved into saturated (7.5 g) and unsaturated (41.5 g) fractions.

Paper and thin layer chromatographic studies showed the presence of palmitic, oleic, linoleic, linolenic and stearic acids.

The fatty acid methyl esters were analysed by gas liquid chromatography using a column of Rheoplex 400-15% supported by chrom-W acid

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